

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetic resources

Panicle characteristics of some *Glaberrima* cultivars

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One approach to increasing grain filling is to decrease the number of secondary branches on the panicle, since spikelets on those branches usually have poor grain filling. Grain filling may be affected by panicle morphology, anatomy, and the transport system. *Glaberrimas* are generally known to have few secondary branches on their panicles.

We studied 12 panicle characteristics in 16 *glaberrima* and 5 *sativa* cultivars from the International Rice Germplasm Center and the Plant Breeding Department of IRRI to study spikelet distribution on primary and secondary

branches and their relationships to other characters.

The main culm and two primary tillers from each cultivar were sampled just after complete panicle exertion.

All characters except culm thickness varied widely among cultivars (Table 1).

Number of primary branches was generally higher in *glaberrimas* than in *sativas*. Number of primary branches among the *glaberrimas* ranged from 8.0 in Acc. 104233 and Acc. 104254 to 16.3 in Acc. 104003 (the highest). The *sativas*, mostly IR cultivars, had higher numbers of secondary branches. The ratio of secondary branches to primary branches did not exceed 2 in the *glaberrimas* (except in Acc. 104233, 104235, and 104254), but in the *sativas*, the ratio was more than 2. Acc. nos. 103350, 103443, 102198, and 103997 had high numbers of primary branches with very few secondary branches; spikelets on secondary branches totaled less than 20% of total spikelets. Acc. 104001 and

Acc. 104003 had high numbers of primary and secondary branches, with spikelets on secondary branches totaling only 30% of the total spikelets. In the *sativas*, spikelets on secondary branches totaled 58% or higher.

The number of vascular bundles from just below the neck node is usually correlated with the number of primary branches. Acc. 103443 had the highest number of inner and outer vascular bundles and also high numbers of primary branches, possibly indicating a better transport system. Acc. 103443 also had the largest culm diameter and medullary cavity.

The number of primary branches and spikelets on primary branches were positively correlated with number of inner and outer vascular bundles (Table 2). These two characters had no relation with number of secondary branches or spikelets on secondary branches, indicating scope for increasing the number of spikelets on the primary

Table 1. Panicle characteristics in *O. glaberrima* and *O. sativa* cultivars. IRRI, 1987.^a

Cultivar	PB (no.)	SB (no.)	SB/PB	SPB (no.)	SSB		TSP (no.)	IVB (no.)	OVB (no.)	CD (mm)	MC (mm)	CTh (mm)
					no.	% of TSP						
<i>O. glaberrima</i>												
Acc. 102318	14.0	8.7	0.6	108	20	16	128	17.0	23.0	2.0	1.4	0.3
Acc. 103350	15.4	4.0	0.3	123	9	7	132	17.3	25.7	2.2	1.4	0.4
Acc. 103437	12.0	7.3	0.6	89	20	18	109	14.4	22.3	2.1	1.0	0.5
Acc. 103438	13.2	2.2	0.2	92	5	5	97	15.0	22.0	2.0	1.1	0.4
Acc. 103443	15.3	11.3	0.7	124	26	17	150	18.7	36.0	2.6	1.8	0.4
Acc. 104026	13.0	17.3	1.3	97	47	33	144	14.0	21.7	2.1	1.2	0.4
Acc. 104233	8.0	22.0	2.7	54	59	52	113	14.7	22.3	2.0	1.2	0.4
Acc. 104235	8.7	20.3	2.3	57	52	48	109	15.0	22.0	2.1	1.3	0.4
Acc. 104254	8.0	27.7	3.5	51	79	61	130	15.0	22.0	2.2	1.3	0.4
Acc. 102198	15.7	6.0	0.4	122	13	10	135	14.7	23.7	1.8	1.0	0.4
Acc. 103995	12.3	7.3	0.6	98	16	14	114	13.7	17.3	1.9	1.1	0.4
Acc. 103997	15.0	11.0	0.7	125	24	16	149	16.7	26.7	1.8	1.1	0.4
Acc. 103999	13.3	5.0	0.4	79	12	13	91	16.0	24.3	1.6	0.8	0.4
Acc. 104001	16.0	22.7	1.4	139	60	30	199	18.0	27.0	2.4	1.4	0.5
Acc. 104003	16.3	18.7	1.1	126	56	31	182	17.7	28.3	2.1	1.4	0.4
Acc. 104013	13.7	14.0	1.0	105	34	24	139	15.3	25.0	2.0	1.2	0.4
<i>O. sativa</i>												
IR20	10.2	34.0	3.3	53	117	67	170	23.0	21.5	2.5	2.0	0.3
IR30	10.7	24.8	2.3	54	87	62	141	23.7	22.2	2.5	2.0	0.3
IR36	9.2	22.8	2.5	50	72	59	122	17.7	20.8	2.1	1.5	0.3
IR60	9.8	21.7	2.2	52	73	58	125	17.7	19.0	2.1	1.5	0.3
IR66	10.0	29.8	3.0	57	100	64	157	19.0	19.7	2.1	1.6	0.3
LSD (0.05)	1.2	4.1		14	14		12	1.2	1.8	0.1	0.1	0.1

^aPB = primary branch, SB = secondary branch, SPB = spikelet on PB, SSB = spikelet on SB, TSP = total spikelets, IVB = inner vascular bundle, OVB = outer vascular bundle, CD = culm diameter, MC = medullary cavity, CTh = culm thickness.

branch without significantly increasing those on the secondary branch.

Medullary cavity was positively correlated with the number of inner and outer vascular bundles and with culm diameter. These characters may be utilized as selection criteria. Culm thickness had no relation with any of the characters, and had minimum variability.

Acc. nos. 103350, 103443, 102198, 103997, 104001, and 104003, with higher numbers of primary branches, spikelets on primary branches, and inner and outer vascular bundles and larger culm

Table 2. Relationship between 10 panicle characters in *O. glaberrima*. IRRI, 1987.

	PB	SB	SPB	SSB	TSP	IVB	OVB	CD	MC
SB	-0.46ns								
SPB	0.96**	-0.34ns							
SSB	-0.46ns	0.99**	-0.35ns						
TSP	0.56*	0.45ns	0.68**	0.44ns					
IVB	0.60*	0.03ns	0.62**	0.02ns	0.61*				
OVB	0.54*	0.04ns	0.55*	0.02ns	0.54*	0.85**			
CD	0.08ns	0.40ns	0.22ns	0.39ns	0.51*	0.49ns	0.55*		
MC	0.18ns	0.35ns	0.31ns	0.32ns	0.55*	0.67**	0.65**	0.87**	
CTh	0.05ns	0.16ns	0.11ns	0.18ns	0.25ns	-0.04ns	0.07ns	0.28ns	-0.15ns

diameter and medullary cavity may be used in breeding for increased numbers of primary branches and numbers of

spikelets on the primary branches. We have made 50 crosses involving these parents for evaluation. □

***eui* gene for elongated uppermost internode transferred to indica rice**

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The *eui*, a recessive gene controlling the elongated uppermost internode in rice, was discovered by Drs. J. N. Rutger and H. L. Carnahan at Davis, California, USA. The gene nearly doubled the length of the uppermost internode, increased panicle length 12%, and had little or no effect on other internodes or

IR50-*eui* rice plant compared to IR50. IRRI, 1987.

Comparative performance of IR50-*eui* and IR50. IRRI, 1987 DS.

Trait	IR50- <i>eui</i>	IR50	Difference ^a
Days to flowering	84	83	
Height (cm)	110.7	64.3	+46.4**
Tillers (no./hill)	25	35	-10.0**
% <i>eui</i> tillers	91.0	0	+91.0**
Yield (g/plant)	18.1	22.3	- 4.2ns

^a ** = significant at 1% level based on *t*-test of mean values. ns = nonsignificant based on *t*-test of mean values.

plant characters. It is considered equivalent to a recessive tall trait.

If the gene were incorporated into the paternal parent of hybrid rice, this parent would be taller. A taller restorer parent would aid windblown pollen dispersal on the semidwarf male sterile female parent in hybrid seed production plots. The resulting F₁ hybrid would, however, be semidwarf. Additionally, a taller restorer parent would facilitate its removal before bulk harvest of the commercial hybrid seed borne on the male sterile parent.

This gene was originally identified in a japonica line having limited use in tropical hybrid rice breeding. Original *eui* genetic stock obtained from Dr. Rutger in 1982 was crossed with semidwarf indica restorer IR50. From the F₂ population of this cross, plants showing the uppermost elongated internode were backcrossed to IR50 three times. In every BCF₂ generation, we selected plants possessing *eui* trait and resembling IR50. The BC₃F₃ progenies homozygous for *eui* gene were

selected and designated IR50-*eui* (see figure). Compared with IR50, IR50-*eui* is significantly taller, has 90% tillers with *eui* trait, but somewhat lower tillering (see table). Yields are not statistically different. Seeds of IR50-*eui* are available at IRRI.

5460ps: indica photosensitive genic male-sterile rice

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Fujian indica photosensitive genic male-sterile germplasm (FIPGMG) 5460ps, isolated from the spontaneous mutant of indica variety 5460, was released in Apr 1988 for developing two-line hybrid rice in China. 5460, as the restorer line for common three-line hybrid rice, was bred in 1983 from an early-maturing mutant (by radiation) of IR54.